

D2.4 Workshop proceedings

Directed evolution of proteins in Košice, Slovakia

Name of project: **Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern
Slovakia (CasProt)**
No. 952333

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Workshop on Directed evolution of proteins took part in Košice in the Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences at Jesenna 5, Košice from May 2nd to May 5th 2023. The intention of the Workshop was to get together experts on protein evolution and on protein design and particularly on protein expression, the topic very closely related to evolution and design new, very often unstable and hard-to-express and purify proteins. The main speaker with the introductory plenary lecture was Prof. Dr. Andreas Plückthun from the partners laboratory of University of Zurich (UZH). We took the opportunity to utilize this Workshop for networking with colleagues from the Czech republic (3 speakers - BIOCEV institute in Prague, Palacky University in Olomouc, and Masaryk University in Brno) and Comenius University in Bratislava

(1 speaker) and Neuroimmunology Institute of Slovak Academy of Sciences in Bratislava (1 speaker). As the workshop took place at the same time as the Summer school on Directed evolution of proteins, numerous students used the opportunity to attend the lectures. This “joint” meeting has been accepted with great satisfaction from both speakers and audience point of views. Lectures on the Workshop consisted of 9 lectures of principal investigators and three lectures of senior researchers.

The program and the location of the Workshop offered numerous possibilities for discussions of young researchers with the principal investigators as well as for establishing new connections and networking among principal investigators.

Overall, the Workshop on Directed evolution of proteins was a successful event. The participants could take part in lectures presenting current topics in protein design and protein evolution and particularly practical problems connected with the expression and purification of proteins evolved/developed by protein engineering methods. This event provided numerous opportunities to discuss scientific projects between young researchers and experienced principal investigators, as well as to discuss potential future joint projects in the blooming field of protein engineering and evolution.

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1. WORKSHOP PROGRAM

Workshop on directed evolution of proteins

Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, Jesenná 5, Košice

May 2nd, 2023 – Tuesday

9:00	<i>Welcome and opening remarks - Erik Sedlák</i>	
9:05-9:50	Andreas Plückthun:	Protein evolution
10:05-10:50	Daniel Rozbesky:	Mammalian cell-based protein production
11:05-11:50	Lenka Džúrová:	Molecular Farming in Barley

May 3rd, 2023 – Wednesday

9:00-9:45	Martin Toul:	Rational protein engineering driven by kinetics
10:00-10:45	Michal Nemergut:	Identifying a new aggregation hotspot in Alzheimer's disease: Opportunities for drug discovery
11:00-11:45	Ľuboš Ambro:	Production and purification of recombinant proteins: pitfalls and problem solving

May 4th, 2023 – Thursday

9:00-9:45	Stanislav Stuchlík:	Solubility as a challenge for expression and purification of recombinant proteins
10:05-10:50	Rostislav Škrabana:	Preparation of intrinsically disordered proteins; their structure and biophysics
11:05-11:50	Veronika Hovanová:	From macroscopic measurements to microscopic events

May 5th, 2023 – Friday

9:00-9:45	Gabriel Žoldák:	The application of nanomechanical studies for protein engineering
10:00-10:45	Veronika Huntošová:	Fluorescence and imaging of proteins in cells
11:00-11:45	Erik Sedlák:	Genetically encoded photosensitizers
12:00	<i>Closing remarks - Erik Sedlák</i>	

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

2. PRESENTATIONS

2.1 Protein evolution

Andreas Plückthun

Abstract: Ribosome display has proven to be a powerful *in vitro* selection and evolution method for generating high-affinity binders from libraries of folded proteins. It has been successfully applied to single-chain Fv fragments of antibodies and alternative scaffolds, such as Designed Ankyrin Repeat Proteins (DARPin) and Armadillo Proteins. High-affinity binders with new target specificity can be obtained from highly diverse DARPins libraries in only a few selection rounds. In this presentation, the selection from the library and the process of affinity maturation and off-rate selection are explained in detail. Natural armadillo repeat proteins like importin- α or β -catenin bind their target peptides such that each repeat interacts with a dipeptide unit within the stretched target peptide. However, this modularity is imperfect and also restricted to short peptide stretches of usually four to six consecutive amino acids. Here the development and characterization of a regularized and truly modular peptide-specific binding protein is presented, based on designed armadillo repeat proteins, binding to peptides of alternating lysine and arginine residues.

Protein evolution (selected slides)

DARPin are multifunctional molecules

Protein evolution (selected slides)

Protein evolution (selected slides)

A

Importin- α

Np1 (1EE5)

Myc (1EE4)

pCN (1Q1S)

α IBB (1IAL)

Nup50 (3TJ3)

consensus **KR** X₁₀₋₁₂ **K+X+**

P1'2' minor site 123456 major site

B

β -catenin

xTcf-3 (1G3J)

ICAT (1LUJ)

APC (1TH1)

hTcf-4 (2GL7)

E_{cyto} (3IFQ)

hLef-1 (3OUW)

consensus **D** X **Q** X **Q** X₂₋₇ **E**

2.2 Mammalian cell-based protein production

Daniel Rozbesky

Abstract: Expressing proteins in mammalian cells is a common technique used in molecular biology and biotechnology to produce specific proteins for various applications. Mammalian cells are chosen for protein expression when post-translational modifications or proper folding is critical for the protein's function or activity. Here's a general outline of the steps involved in expressing proteins in mammalian cells:

(i) Selecting the Expression System: Common mammalian cell lines used for protein expression include HEK293, CHO (Chinese Hamster Ovary), and HeLa cells. (ii) Gene Cloning: The first step is to isolate and clone the gene of interest into an appropriate expression vector. (iii) Transient Transfection: Transient transfection is a common method for short-term protein expression. (iv) Stable Transfection (Optional): For long-term or continuous protein expression, stable transfection can be performed. (v) Selection and Clonal Expansion (for stable lines): Following transfection, cells are typically subjected to selection using antibiotics or other markers present in the expression vector. Clonal cell lines can be generated to ensure homogeneity in protein expression. (vi) Protein Expression and Harvesting: After successful transfection, the cells will begin producing the protein of interest. (vii) Protein Purification (optional): Depending on the application and downstream use, the protein may require purification to remove contaminants and obtain a pure product. (viii) Protein Characterization. (ix) Storage and Distribution.

It's important to note that protein expression in mammalian cells can be more challenging compared to other expression systems, and factors like codon optimization, signal sequences, and culture conditions may need to be optimized to achieve high-level expression and proper folding of the protein of interest.

Mammalian cell-based protein production (selected slides)

Mammalian cell-based protein production (selected slides)

Transient transfection versus Stable cell lines

Transient transfection:

- transfected DNA is not integrated into the genome
- transfected genetic material is not passed onto the progeny
- protein harvest after a few days
- more expensive than stable transfection (Plasmid Giga Kit - €600)
- faster than stable transfection

Stable cell lines:

- transfected DNA integrates into the genome
- transfected genetic material is carried stably from generation to generation
- uniform and indefinite protein production

Transient transfection – adherent cells

Mammalian cell-based protein production (selected slides)

Transfection reagents

- Stable complex formation with DNA
- Efficient cell entry
- Endosomal escape
- Low cytotoxicity

- Cost efficient: PEI, PEI_{max}
- Lipid-based reagents: Lipo-/Expifectam

- Co-transfection of multiple plasmids

The diagram illustrates the transfection process. On the left, DNA (represented as a blue double helix) and PEI (represented as red plus signs) form a PEI/DNA complex. This complex enters a cell (green oval) and escapes the endosome. In the nucleus, the DNA is transcribed into RNA. The RNA then moves to the cytoplasm where it is translated by ribosomes into protein. The protein is then folded into its functional shape.

Expression vectors for transient transfection

The diagram shows the pOPINF vector (5555bp) with various components: Amp^r, Lef-2, 633, CMV enhancer, Chicken actin promoter, T7 promoter/lac operator, p10 promoter + 5' UTR, 5' Infusion site (KpnI) N-His-3C tag, lacZ promoter/gene insert, 3' Infusion site (HindIII), beta globin polyA signal, T7 terminator, and Ori1629. The Origin (pUC) is also indicated.

C-tags

- C-His
- 3C-eGFPwYFP/BFP2mCherry-His
- 3C-HALO7
- 3C-CD4
- 3C-Fc
- 3C-BirA
- C-His

N-tags

- N-His-3C
- POI
- SUMO
- TRX
- MSYB
- GFP
- GST
- HALO7
- MSP
- TF
- NusA

PCR products can be used to create a family of fusion proteins for expression in different hosts.

Legend: ■ His₆ tag ■ 3C cleavage site ■ Signal sequence ■ Protein of interest

pTriEx2 based vectors
In-Fusion cloning

Berrow NS et al. Nucleic Acids Res, 2007

2.3 Molecular Farming in Barley

Lenka Džúrová

Abstract: Molecular farming, also known as biopharming or molecular agriculture, is a biotechnology approach that involves using genetically modified plants to produce valuable pharmaceutical proteins, industrial enzymes, or other high-value compounds. Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) is one of the crop species that has been explored for molecular farming due to its advantages, such as well-established transformation techniques, fast growth, and a relatively large seed size that facilitates protein extraction.

Molecular farming in barley holds great promise as it provides an alternative and potentially cost-effective method for producing valuable proteins compared to traditional expression systems like bacteria or mammalian cells. However, the use of genetically modified crops for molecular farming also raises concerns regarding biosafety, environmental impact, and potential cross-contamination with food crops, so rigorous safety measures and regulations are essential when conducting such research and development.

Molecular Farming in Barley (selected slides)

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Czech Advanced
Technological Research
Institute

Genetic manipulation of plants

- Genetic modification / engineering
- Altering the genome of different organisms by the use of:
 1. Conventional methods: selective breeding and crossbreeding to produce desired traits in plants and animals
 2. Molecular methods: gene cloning: product is genetically modified organism (GMO)

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Czech Advanced
Technological Research
Institute

Recombinant protein/ peptide production

- Proteins or peptides for various purposes: medicine, cosmetics, research or industry
- Production system:
 - time spent in expressing the protein
 - ease of handling the expression system
 - amount of protein needed
 - mass of the protein
 - type of post-translational modifications, number of disulfide bonds
 - destination of the expressed protein
- Variety of expression systems:
 - Prokaryotic: bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Corynebacterium*, *Bacillus subtilis*)
 - Eukaryotic: yeasts (*Pichia pastoris*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) or filamentous fungi (*Claviceps purpurea*, *Fusarium verticillioides*), mammalian/insect cell cultures, transgenic animals, transgenic plants

Molecular Farming in Barley (selected slides)

CATRIN
Czech Advanced Technology Research Institute

Molecular farming

using plants as host for production of valuable proteins

- No need for expensive bioreactors as for cell cultures
- Easy scalability in the field/greenhouse
- Low risk of contamination by human pathogens or endotoxins
- Allow non-native proteins to be synthesized with proper folding and activity

BUT

- Genetic modification of plants more complicated
- Different posttranslational modification (glycosylation, disulfide bonds, ...)
- Expression in whole plant – often retarded growth
- GMO issues

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Czech Advanced Technology Research Institute

Molecular farming in green barley

- Hordeum vulgare* cultivar Golden promise

BBCH77 stage (Crop Identification and BBCH Staging Manual: SMAP-12 Field Campaign; Oklahoma State University, 2011).

- Well- established gene transfer technology
- Cost- effective production
- Harvesting of final product in late milky endosperm stage (BBCH77):
 - freeze drying → long-term storage without loss of its quality
 - no risk of a transgene escape under natural conditions, the grain is not able to reproduce
 - **The harvested product is NOT GMO** (an advantage in terms of legislation)!

Molecular Farming in Barley (selected slides)

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Agrobacterium mediated in-planta transformation

- Genetic information for tumor growth (T-DNA) substituted with gene of interest
- Does not involve plant tissue culture

Techniques:

- 1. Agroinoculation:** transformation through the surface of the plant tissue. Done by a toothpick, wire loop, or direct organ immersion (floral dip method, cocultivation of immature embryos with Agro).
- 2. Agroinfiltration:** done by a syringe or vacuum onto the underside of the leaf while applying pressure on the other side of the leaf.

Chen et al., 2013

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Protocol of Agrotransformation

Stage I

- Preparation of sterilize seed or samples
- Immature embryo or embryogenic
- Plasmid contraction and *Agrobacterium* preparation
- Preparation of inoculum

Stage II

- Explant preparation, inoculation/infection and co-cultivation with *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*

Stage III

- Selection

Stage IV

- Regeneration

Stage V

- Acclimatization and molecular identification of T₀ Plant

Stage VI

- Cultivation and self-crossing of T₀ Plant

Stage VII

- T₁ plant analysis

DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.91132

2.4 Rational protein engineering driven by kinetics

Martin Toul

Abstract: Rational protein engineering driven by kinetics is a strategy used to design and modify proteins based on their kinetics, which refers to the rates of enzyme-catalyzed reactions or ligand-binding events. This approach focuses on understanding the molecular mechanisms that govern the protein's function and using this knowledge to engineer proteins with improved or novel properties. Applications of rational protein engineering driven by kinetics can be diverse and include improving the efficiency of enzymes used in industrial processes, developing more effective biocatalysts for pharmaceutical production, enhancing the specificity of ligand-binding proteins, and designing novel enzymes with desired properties not found in nature.

Overall, rational protein engineering guided by kinetics offers a powerful and systematic approach to engineer proteins with specific kinetic properties, contributing to advancements in various fields of biotechnology, medicine, and biochemistry.

Rational protein engineering driven by kinetics (selected slides)

Rational protein engineering driven by kinetics (selected slides)

Enzyme kinetics

ENZYME ACTIVITY

$$E + S \xrightarrow{k} E + P$$

STEADY-STATE KINETICS

$$E + S \xrightleftharpoons{K_m} E.S \xrightarrow{k_{cat}} E + P$$

PRE-STEADY-STATE KINETICS

$$E + S \xrightleftharpoons[k_{-1}]{k_{+1}} E.S \xrightleftharpoons[k_{-2}]{k_{+2}} E.I \xrightleftharpoons[k_{-3}]{k_{+3}} E.P \xrightleftharpoons[k_{-4}]{k_{+4}} E + P$$

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Rational engineering

IN SILICO

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

ADVANCED KINETICS

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Rational protein engineering driven by kinetics (selected slides)

Studied proteins

1. Haloalkane dehalogenase

2. Thrombolytic enzymes

6

Dehalogenase

$$E + S \xrightleftharpoons{K_s} E.S \xrightleftharpoons[k_{-2}]{k_{+2}} E.I \xrightarrow{\times} E.P \xrightleftharpoons{K_d} E + P$$

■ LinB-wt
■ LinB-H272F
■ LinB-H272N

Parameter	LinB-wt	LinB-H272F	LinB-H272N
$K_d (Cl^-)$ [mM]	~300	~200	~250
K_s [µM]	~100	~300	~200
k_{+2} [s ⁻¹]	~100	~0.02	~8
k_{-2} [s ⁻¹]	~30	~0.08	~0.008
$K_{+2} (= k_{+2}/k_{-2})$	~2	~0.025	~1000

Covalent bond between HaloTag® protein and chloroalkane ligand + functional group.

Gao et al., CSBJ 2023 (under review)

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2.5 Identifying a new aggregation hotspot in Alzheimer's disease: Opportunities for drug discovery

Michal Nemerlut

Abstract: Apolipoprotein E (ApoE) $\epsilon 4$ genotype is the most prevalent risk factor for late-onset Alzheimer's Disease (AD). Although ApoE4 differs from its non-pathological ApoE3 isoform only by the C112R mutation, the molecular mechanism of its proteinopathy is unknown. Here, we reveal the molecular mechanism of ApoE4 aggregation using a combination of experimental and computational techniques, including X-ray crystallography, site-directed mutagenesis, hydrogen-deuterium mass spectrometry (HDX-MS), static light scattering and molecular dynamics simulations. Treatment of ApoE $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ and $\epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$ cerebral organoids with tramiprosate was used to compare the effect of tramiprosate on ApoE4 aggregation at the cellular level.

We found that C112R substitution in ApoE4 induces long-distance ($>15 \text{ \AA}$) conformational changes leading to the formation of a V-shaped dimeric unit that is geometrically different and more aggregation-prone than the ApoE3 structure. AD drug candidate tramiprosate and its metabolite 3-sulfopropanoic acid induce ApoE3-like conformational behavior in ApoE4 and reduce its aggregation propensity. Analysis of ApoE $\epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$ cerebral organoids treated with tramiprosate revealed its effect on cholesteryl esters, the storage products of excess cholesterol.

Our results connect the ApoE4 structure with its aggregation propensity, providing a new druggable target for neurodegeneration and aging.

Identifying a new aggregation hotspot in Alzheimer's disease: Opportunities for drug discovery (selected slides)

What causes Alzheimer's disease?

Healthy brain size
Shrunken brain with Alzheimer disease
Dying neuron with tangles
Plaque
Healthy neuron

Tramiprosate – anti-A β oligomer agent

Alzheim Prodrug ALZ-801
Tramiprosate

Amyloid beta (A β) accumulates into plaques that are considered a hallmark of a brain affected by Alzheimer's.

The first oral drug in AD treatment developed by company Alzheim.

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Amyloid hypothesis

Non-Amyloidogenic Pathway | Amyloidogenic Pathway

Extracellular space
Inter-Membrane space
Cytoplasm

P3, sAPP α , APP, sAPP β , A β 42 Monomers, Toxic A β Oligomers, Amyloid Plaques

γ -Sec, α -Sec, β -Sec, γ -Sec

AICD, CTF α , CTF β , AICD

doi: 10.1002/med.21434

APP – Amyloid Precursor Protein

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Identifying a new aggregation hotspot in Alzheimer's disease: Opportunities for drug discovery (selected slides)

ApoE (Apolipoprotein E) Cascade Hypothesis

The biochemical and biophysical properties of ApoE impact a cascade of events at the cellular and systems levels, which ultimately contribute to pathogenic conditions and AD disease development.

doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2022.03.004

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Apolipoprotein E (ApoE)

Basic characteristics:

- Two-domain protein component of lipoprotein particles
- Transport of cholesterol throughout the brain
- **Key regulator of Aβ aggregation and clearance**
- Exists as three common isoforms
 - ApoE2 (112C, 158C)
 - ApoE3 (112C, 158R)
 - ApoE4 (112R, 158R) ☹️
- ApoE4 is the strongest genetic risk factor for AD!

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Identifying a new aggregation hotspot in Alzheimer's disease: Opportunities for drug discovery (selected slides)

Analysis of ApoE crystal packing

The individual NTDs interact through the same „self-association“ interface.

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Superposition of all solved ApoE crystal structures

T-shaped packing

- ApoE2: 1LE2, 1NF0
- ApoE3: 1LPE, 1NFN
1BZ4, 1EA8
1H7I, 6V7M
- ApoE4: 1B68, 1LE4
- ApoE4 + corrector:
6NCN, 6NCO
- ApoE4 mutants:
7FCR, 7FCS

Superposition

V-shaped packing

- ApoE3: 1OR2, 1OR3
- ApoE4: 1GS9, 8AX8
8AX9, 8CDY
8CE0

ApoE4 prefers a geometrically different crystal packing than ApoE3.

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2.6 Production and purification of recombinant proteins: pitfalls and problem solving

Ľuboš Ambro

Abstract: Recombinant protein expression frequently necessitates rigorous planning and process optimization to determine the ideal host, culture condition, as well as the best feasible purification technique to ensure a high yield with the fewest possible quality lost. Both protein expression and purification are frequently difficult and complex processes because of the overall complexity that proteins have by nature. There is no "one size fits all" method, and the expression and purification of each protein need to be tailored to the specific situation. The lecture will discuss the most often problems encountered during the process of protein production in *E. coli* with a particular focus on cloning, expression, and purification steps.

Production and purification of recombinant proteins: pitfalls and problem solving (selected slides)

PROTEIN PRODUCTION

- **Basic research** = role of proteins in cell processes / interactions / stability / structural biology
- **Production for the purpose of therapy / diagnostics** = hormones (HGF, insulin), coagulation factors, various enzymes used in biotechnology = antibodies, interferons, proteins used in vaccines
- **Biotechnology** = various enzymes (proteases, xylanases, etc.)

PROCESS OF PROTEIN PRODUCTION

- Everything starts with cloning...

```

    graph TD
      A[Gene of interest] --> B[Full-length cDNA]
      B --> C[Insert into expression vector]
      C --> D[Clone into suitable expression system]
      D --> E[Screen for positive clones]
      E --> F[Select the best construct/expression host]
      F --> G[Mammalian cells]
      F --> H[Bacteria, yeast and insect cells]
      G --> I[Expand the transient/stable transfectants]
      I --> J[Cell-based studies]
      H --> K[Scale up]
      K --> L[Isolate and purify protein of interest]
      L --> M[MOSTLY, THIS IS NOT THE END]
  
```

After several unsuccessful rounds
 Study protein Optimize expression
 YES ↑ ↑ NO
 Is there improvement?
 Optimize expression
 Optimize purification
 ↑
 Protein yield is low
 Low protein / contaminants ratio
 Protein is aggregates after purification

Production and purification of recombinant proteins: pitfalls and problem solving (selected slides)

MOLECULAR CLONING: screening of recombinants

- Blue-white screening can be used (requires appropriate vector + host strain for β -Gal complementation)

- Alternatively, colony PCR is performed to screen for recombinants
- Final construct must be sequenced to verify correct sequence / orientation of inserted gene

EXPRESSION SYSTEMS

	<u>ADVANTAGES</u>	<u>DRAWBACKS</u>
<i>E. coli</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rapid expression Less expensive Simple process scale-up Well characterized genetics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No eukaryotic post-translational modifications Some proteins are not properly folded Proteins are rarely secreted
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately rapid expression Works well for secreted and intracellular proteins Less expensive Most protein folding and post-translational modifications are possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Glycan structures of proteins are different from typical mammalian proteins Requires use of yeast secretion signal peptides Enhanced safety precautions are required

Production and purification of recombinant proteins: pitfalls and problem solving (selected slides)

PROTEIN PURIFICATION: a pipeline

AIM: obtain high-purity protein for any downstream application

Selection of purification methods is based on

- Protein characteristics (size, hydrophobic or hydrophilic? charge, solubility)
- Desired quantity of the protein
- Level of purity needed

FOR TAGGED PROTEINS: Affinity chromatography → Size exclusion chromatography
 FOR UNTAGGED PROTEINS: Ion exchange chromatography → Size exclusion chromatography

- Gravity columns vs. HPLC-based purification
- BASIC STEPS: 1) cell lysis (buffer = pH, ionic strength, protease inhibitors + OPTIONALLY: detergents, glycerol, DTT / BME, other additives. 2) protein binding to a specific matrix, 3) washing and 4) elution

Size exclusion chromatography

Separates molecules by their sizes and molecular weight

- Used as a **polishing step** in protein purification pipeline (after IMAC / IEC)
- + Does not require a binding and elution protocol
- + The mildest purification option and preserves the biological activity of target molecules

For first choice for high-resolution fractionation, short run times, and high recovery:

Superdex 75: 3 - 600 kDa

Superdex 200: 10 - 6000 kDa

@ STATIONARY PHASE: agarose / agarose-dextran composite = small beads. Various SEC resins available (Superdex, Superose, Sephacryl = various columns and fractionation range: Small protein? Large protein? Complexes? Antibodies?)

@ MOBILE PHASE: any desired buffer, working pH range 3–12, stable in 1 M acetic acid, 8 M urea, 6 M guanidine hydrochloride, 1% SDS, organic solvents

2.7 Solubility as a challenge for expression and purification of recombinant proteins

Stanislav Stuchlík

Abstract: Soluble expression of recombinant proteins is one of the main obstacles to receive properly folded and biologically active molecules for their applications, like structural studies, producing therapeutics, industrial enzymes, etc. There are several strategies of recombinant protein expression and purification to overcome undesired protein misfolding/aggregation. In this presentation, we were focused mainly to the following solutions: to „slow down“ of proteosynthesis (e.g., by lower cultivation temperature, using minimal media, using host strains like *E. coli* ArcticExpres or other host organisms), using soluble fusion partners for protein expression (e.g. Trx, SUMO, etc.) and directed protein evolution by specific modeling software with following site-directed PCR mutagenesis. We have also used and developed a host expression system based on the prokaryotic bacteria *Vibrio natriegens* which can be permeabilized by co-expression of specific carboxypeptidases during target protein expression, and thus to direct produced recombinant protein to cultivation media to receive soluble expressed proteins.

Solubility as a challenge for expression and purification of recombinant proteins
(selected slides)

The first published example of soluble recombinant protein expression

FNR – Fumarate Nitrate Regulator - CAP like protein

- Anaerobic metabolism of *E. coli*
- Fe-S clusters in protein structure

Stuchlík, S. and Turňa, J. Overexpression of the FNR protein of *Escherichia coli* with the T7 expression system. *Folia Microbiologica* 43, 601-604, 1998

Strategies of recombinant protein soluble expression (to overcome undesired protein misfolding/aggregation)

- „Slow down“ of proteosynthesis:
 - Lower cultivation temperature
 - Minimal media
 - Other host strain – e.g. *E. coli* Arctic Express, and other hosts (yeasts, etc...)
- Use of soluble fusion partners (e.g. Trx, SUMO, etc.)
- Directed evolution by mutagenesis
- Recombinant protein secretion to media and/or membrane permeabilization

Solubility as a challenge for expression and purification of recombinant proteins (selected slides)

Soluble expression and purification of ITP/ITPL neuropeptides from insects with Trx fusion partner

Ion transport peptide (ITP) from *Drosophila melanogaster* and *Bombyx mori*
 Ion transport peptide-like (ITPL) from *D. melanogaster*
 Insect physiology and lipid metabolism study - cooperation with Inst. Zool SAS

The diagram illustrates the physiological role of ITP in insects. ITP is shown as a central red circle with arrows pointing to three boxes: 'Sůl, pitvan vody' (Salt, water intake), 'Hlad, pitvan potraviny' (Hunger, food intake), and 'Exkréce, inhibice vyhledávání vody' (Excretion, inhibition of water seeking). These three boxes have arrows pointing to a final box: 'Tělesné tekutiny' (Body fluids), with an upward arrow indicating an increase.

Purification of recombinant insect ITP/ITPL neuropeptides

IMAC/ANEX/SEC
 High number of Cysteins

1) Ladder SeeBlue Plus2 2) frakcia nezachytených proteínov (flow through) z IMAC 3) elúcia z IMAC 4) vzorka po dialýze 5) vzorka po lyofilizácii

1) Ladder SeeBlue Plus2 2) elúcia z IMAC 3) frakcia po ANEX

1) Ladder SeeBlue Plus2 2) vzorka po 24 hodinovej inkubácii s 2 U antibiotikami 3) frakcia nezachytených proteínov (flow through) z IMAC chromatografie 4) frakcia po presušenom kroku z IMAC chromatografie 5) elúcia z IMAC chromatografie 6) vzorka po dialýze 7) vzorka po lyofilizácii

Solubility as a challenge for expression and purification of recombinant proteins
(selected slides)

**Directed protein evolution (*RrADH*)
by predictive software tool Aggrescan 3D 2.0**

3x AA exchanged to arginine –
2-fold increased solubility

In silico selection of aggregative sites suitable
for aminoacid exchange to increase a solubility

Insertion of mutations by site specific PCR;
fragments fusion to functional fragment of ADH-A
gene and restriction analysis confirmation

Western blot analysis of wt ADH-A
and mutated variant ADH-Amut2

Minich A. et al. Enhancement of solubility of recombinant alcohol dehydrogenase from *Rhodococcus ruber* using predictive tool. *World J Microbiol Biotechnol* 38(11):214,2022.

***Vibrio natriegens* as novel host bacteria
for heterologous expression**

- *Vibrio natriegens* (known in the past also as *Pseudomonas natriegens*, *Beneckea natriegens* - non-pathogenic gram-negative marine bacterium found in salt marsh mud - GRAS
- doubling generation time is < 10 min, what is 2-3- fold faster than for *Escherichia coli*.
- cca 115 000 ribosomes/generation (*E. coli* ~ 70 000 ribosomes/generation).
- Increased number of tRNA gene caused by stronger promoter activity (*V. natriegens* has +30 tRNA genes more than *E. coli*)

Growth of *V. natriegens* (Vn) a *E. coli* (Ec)
in time intervals.

a

Time (min)	<i>V. natriegens</i> (strain A)	<i>E. coli</i> BL21 (DE3)	<i>E. coli</i> NEB Turbo	<i>E. coli</i> EP006
0	0	0	0	0
100	~8	~2	~1	~0.5
200	~12	~4	~2	~1
300	~14	~6	~3	~1.5
400	~15	~8	~4	~2
500	~16	~10	~5	~2.5

b

6h

Strain	17 A 5	BL21 DE3
<i>V. nat</i>	High turbidity	Low turbidity
<i>E. coli</i>	High turbidity	Low turbidity

2.8 Preparation of intrinsically disordered proteins; their structure and biophysics

Rostislav Škrabana

Abstract: Intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs) are a class of proteins that lack a well-defined three-dimensional structure under physiological conditions. Unlike traditional globular proteins with stable folded structures, IDPs exhibit high conformational flexibility and can adopt a wide range of conformations. Despite their lack of a fixed structure, IDPs play crucial roles in various cellular processes, including signaling, regulation, and molecular recognition. Preparing IDPs for structural and biophysical studies can be challenging due to their inherently dynamic nature. Here were discussed some methods and techniques used for the preparation, study of structure, and biophysics of IDPs. Due to their importance in cellular processes and their unique biophysical properties, IDPs have gained significant attention in the field of structural biology and biophysics. Understanding the structure and biophysics of IDPs is essential for unraveling their functional mechanisms and exploring their potential as therapeutic targets.

Preparation of intrinsically disordered proteins; their structure and biophysics (selected slides)

Globular versus disordered proteins

- Globular proteins have stable and well-defined 3D structure
- In contrast, Intrinsically Disordered Proteins (IDPs) have no stable structure and exists as **conformational ensemble**
- Intrinsically Disordered Regions (IDRs) may exists in some globular proteins
- There is a continuum of protein structure and disorder

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Nature of IDP conformational ensemble

IDPs are **compositionally** and **sequentially** biased: they are enriched in polar/charged amino acids whereas depleted in hydrophobic aa.

Consequently, IDP can be fairly well predicted from sequence (around 80 % accuracy)

More than 50 IDP predictors, e.g. IUPRED (<https://iupred3.elte.hu/>)

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Preparation of intrinsically disordered proteins; their structure, and biophysics (selected slides)

Nature of IDP conformational ensemble

Example: neuronal protein tau

Longest human tau40 isoform		
Gly	49	11.1%
Ser	46	10.2%
Lys	44	10.0%
Pro	43	9.8%
Thr	36	7.9%
Ala	34	7.7%
Asp	29	6.8%
Val	27	6.1%
Glu	27	6.1%
Leu	21	4.8%
Gln	19	4.3%
Ile	15	3.4%
Arg	14	3.2%
His	12	2.7%
Asn	11	2.5%
Met	6	1.4%
Tyr	5	1.1%
Phe	3	0.7%
Cys	2	0.5%
Trp	0	0.0%

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Purification of IDPs: example of tau protein

General characteristics: bipolar molecule

Case study: tau protein fragments:

τ 1-223 1 ————— 223 pI = 4.7

τ 221-441 221 ————— 441 pI = 10.6

τ 43 1 — I1 I2 ————— R1 R2 R3 R4 — 441 pI = 10.2

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Preparation of intrinsically disordered proteins; their structure and biophysics
(selected slides)

Isolation of tau protein from tissue

Isolation of tau from brain require a procedure able to preserve native status of e.g. phosphorylation

Exploring low pH stability of tau, intact phosphoepitopes are preserved (combination of perchloric acid/affinity/acetone-TCA procedure)

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Nature of IDP conformational ensemble

Conformational ensemble of tau as seen by NMR and SAXS:

Mukrasch et al 2009 PLoSBiology Mylonas et al 2008 Biochemistry

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2.9 From macroscopic measurements to microscopic events

Veronika Hovanová

Abstract: The protein eADF4(C16), a recombinant spider silk protein derived from the dragline protein *Araneus diadematus* fibroin 4 (ADF4), undergoes the assembly of amyloid-like nanofibrils, which can be used as a foundation for the development of advanced biomaterials with enhanced strength and flexibility. These nanofibrils hold great promise in applications such as tissue engineering, drug delivery systems, and the creation of biodegradable and environmentally friendly materials. The self-assembly and aggregation behavior of the protein eADF4(C16) was investigated under various environmental conditions, such as different pH, kosmotropic and chaotropic salts, and temperatures. Remarkably, eADF4(C16) self-assembles via a nucleation-based mechanism, where secondary nucleation plays a crucial role, independent of the type of kosmotropic anion involved. Chaotropic anions stabilize water-soluble conformers, preventing fibril formation, likely due to direct interactions with the eADF4(C16) polypeptide chain. The temperature was found to accelerate protein self-assembly, but the dominant mechanism of fibrillization remained consistent. At low pH values (pH 3 to 5), the increase in turbidity displayed sigmoidal curves, characteristic of fibril self-assembly. Conversely, no changes in turbidity were observed at pH 6 and higher, indicating the presence of a stable, soluble form of the protein.

From macroscopic measurements to microscopic events (selected slides)

Spider silk

Natural Spider Silk

Dragline silk
Araneus diadematus

Diagram labels: dragline, core, shell, spider, web.

Diagram labels: H₂N, NR, 200, 10-20 amino acids, 20-100 repeats, NR, COOH.

Recombinant Spider Silk

design of typical repetitive motifs (consensus motifs) based on sequences from natural spider silk proteins, optimized for bacterial production

E. coli

purification

eADF4(C16)

module C

GSSAAAAAAAAASGPGYGPENQGPSGPGGYGPGP

H₂N- [16 repeats] -COOH

Huenmarich et al., *Biochemistry*, 2004, 43, 13604-13612.
Heidebrecht et al., *Adv. Appl. Microbiol.* 2013, 82.

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Processing of eADF4(C16)

module C

GSSAAAAAAAAASGPGYGPENQGPSGPGGYGPGP

H₂N- [16 repeats] -COOH

Humenik, M. et al. 2011, *Polymers*, 1, 640-651.

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From macroscopic measurements to microscopic events (selected slides)

Protein processing

Production and processing according to Schacht & Scheibel:

Protein dissolution

Dialysis

Ultracentrifugation

}

6 M Gdn-SCN

10 mM Tris/HCl, pH 8.0

185,000xg, 55 min, 4°C

Hardy and Scheibel, *Biochemical Society Transactions* 37, 2009

Schacht and Scheibel, *Biomacromolecules* 12, 2011

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Protein self-assembly into nanofibrils

aqueous
eADF4(C16)
solution

}

> 250 mM KPi

< 250 mM KPi

phase-separation

nucleation and elongation

Humenik M., Magdeburg M., Scheibel T. (2014) Influence of repeat numbers on self-assembly rates of repetitive recombinant spider silk proteins. *J Struct Biol* 186:431-437.

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From macroscopic measurements to microscopic events (selected slides)

2.10 The application of nanomechanical studies for protein engineering

Gabriel Žoldák

Abstract: Nanomechanical studies have emerged as a powerful tool for protein engineering, allowing researchers to study the mechanical properties of proteins at the nanoscale. By applying forces to individual proteins and measuring their response, researchers can gain insights into how proteins can function in complex biological environments and how they can be optimized for specific applications. Overall, the application of nanomechanical studies for protein engineering has the potential to revolutionize the design and development of biomaterials and protein-based therapeutics. By gaining a deeper understanding of the mechanical properties of proteins, researchers can develop new materials and therapies that are more effective, durable, and tailored to specific applications.

The application of nanomechanical studies for protein engineering
(selected slides)

Protein nanomechanics

How to study protein structural mechanics

- Atomic force microscopy
- Optical tweezers
- Magnetic tweezers
- Acoustic spectroscopy

Zoldák G, Rief M. Force as a single molecule probe of multidimensional protein energy landscapes. *Curr Opin Struct Biol.* 2013 Feb;23(1):48-57.

Selected papers

General information on protein nanomechanics

Case study 1.

Ultrafast folding kinetics and cooperativity of villin headpiece in single-molecule force spectroscopy
Gabriel Zoldák^{1,2}, Johannes Stigler³, Benjamin Peizl⁴, Hongbin Li⁵, and Matthias Rief^{1,2,3}

¹Physik Department E22, Technische Universität München, 85748 Garching, Germany; ²Department of Chemistry, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, Canada V1T 1Z1; and ³Max Planck Center for Integrated Protein Science, 81377 Munich, Germany

678 Biophysical Journal Volume 108 February 2015 678-686

Article

A Compact Native 24-Residue Supersecondary Structure Derived from the Villin Headpiece Subdomain

Henry G. Hocking,^{1,2} Florian Häge,^{1,2} Tobias Madl,^{1,2,4} Martin Zacharias,⁵ Matthias Rief,^{1,2,3} and Gabriel Zoldák^{1,2}

¹Center for Integrated Protein Science Munich, Department Chemie, Technische Universität München, Garching, Germany; ²Institute of Structural Biology, Helmholtz Zentrum München, Neuhering, Germany; ³Physik Department E22, Technische Universität München, Garching, Germany; ⁴Institute of Molecular Biology & Biochemistry, Center of Molecular Medicine, Medical University of Graz, Graz, Austria; ⁵Physik Department E22 and ⁶Center for Integrated Protein Science Munich, Physik Department, Technische Universität München, Garching, Germany

Case study 2.

Nucleotides regulate the mechanical hierarchy between subdomains of the nucleotide binding domain of the Hsp70 chaperone DnaK
Daniela Bauer^{1,2}, Dale R. Merz^{2,3}, Benjamin Peizl⁴, Kelly E. Theisen⁵, Gall Yacynych⁶, Dejana Mokrjanec¹, Ruxandra I. Dima^{1,2}, Matthias Rief^{1,2,3}, and Gabriel Zoldák^{1,2}

¹Physik Department E22, Technische Universität München, 85748 Garching, Germany; ²Department of Chemistry, University of Cincinnati, Cincinnati, OH 45221; ³Department of Physiological Chemistry, Medical Faculty, University of Munich, 81337 Munich, Germany; and ⁴Max Planck Center for Integrated Protein Science, 81377 Munich, Germany

Edited by Robert L. Baldwin, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, and approved June 23, 2015 (received for review March 6, 2015)

The nucleotide binding domain of the Hsp70 chaperone DnaK is composed of two subdomains named I and II.

A folding nucleus and minimal ATP binding domain of Hsp70 identified by single-molecule force spectroscopy
Daniela Bauer^{1,2}, Sarah Meinhold³, Roman P. Jakob⁴, Johannes Stigler⁵, Ulrich Merkel⁶, Timm Maier⁶, Matthias Rief^{1,2,3}, and Gabriel Zoldák^{1,2}

¹Physik Department E22, Technische Universität München, 85748 Garching, Germany; ²Biozentrum, University of Basel, 4056 Basel, Switzerland; ³Gene Center, Ludwig Maximilians University, 81377 Munich, Germany; ⁴Munich Center for Integrated Protein Science, 81377 Munich, Germany; and ⁵Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences, Technology and Innovation Park, P.O. Seifried University, 86174 Kolben, Slovakia

Edited by George H. Lorimer, University of Maryland, College Park, MD, and approved March 23, 2018 (received for review September 26, 2017)

The folding pathways of some proteins are complex, with many of these proteins is composed of two subdomains named I and II.

The application of nanomechanical studies for protein engineering

(selected slides)

Case study 1. finding stable supersecondary structures

Villin headpiece - a model protein

- HP 35 residues wt and N68A/K70M variant
- Ultrafast microsecond folding
- Single-molecule force assays
- Assay for fast data acquisition

Case study 1. finding stable supersecondary structures

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The application of nanomechanical studies for protein engineering
(selected slides)

Case study 2. Repairing of yeast mtHsp70

NBD - a nucleotide binding domain

- ATPase
- consisting lobe I - lobe II
- single-molecule force assay
- rupture is cooperative
- unfolding intermediates

Summary

Villin headpiece - case 1

- Single-molecule force spectroscopy can detect microsecond processes
- Detailed equilibrium analysis can detect stable intermediates
- Finding a stable supersecondary substructure that can be detected also by traditional structural techniques

Yeast mitochondrial mtHsp70 - case 2

- mtHsp70 NBD folding is corrupted, no folding observed in the absence of critical cofactors
- Molecular mechanism behind - lobe II, which is stable in bacteria but unstable in mtHsp70
- Replacing lobe II from mitochondrial NBD for bacterial lobe II rescue the folding and ATPase activity and results in a stable protein

2.11 Fluorescence and imaging of proteins in cells

Veronika Huntošová

Abstract: Cancer cells have developed a concept of how to overcome an imbalance between free radicals and enzymes with antioxidant activity. Despite high mitochondrial oxidative stress, most cancer cells are able to proliferate and promote tumour growth. The use of anticancer drugs can disrupt this balance. Such a principle is used in photodynamic therapy (PDT), which noninvasively increases the level of oxidative stress in cells through the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS). In addition, ROS interacts with the environment and can cause immediate oxidation of lipids and proteins. For this reason, the targeting, localization and specific distribution of ROS is very important. The most important subcellular pool is stored in mitochondria. The application of PDT can disrupt the mitochondrial membrane potential, leading to the opening of the pores and the release of proteins and ROS into the cytoplasm. PDT is a treatment method that uses a light-sensitive molecule, a photosensitizer, and light of an appropriate wavelength. Ideally, the photosensitizer is a molecule that has interesting photodynamic properties for the diagnosis and treatment of cancer cells. Treatment results often differ in cell cultures in monolayers and in tissues under the same conditions. The intermediate stage between these two systems can be defined by 3D spheroids of cells. We have constructed fluorescently labelled designed ankyrin repeat protein (DARPin) to enable targeting of photosensitizer in cancer cells with elevated HER2 receptors. Fluorescence imaging technique as confocal fluorescence 3D reconstruction, co-localisation study and fluorescence lifetime imaging were used to identify the efficacy of HER2 receptors targeting and internalisation of DARPin in cancer cells in 2D and 3D.

Fluorescence and imaging of proteins in cells (selected slides)

DARPin - cell characterisation – immuno staining (antibodies)

CasProt

nuclei

HER2 receptors

SKBR3 cells

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DARPin - cell characterisation

CasProt

(A)

(B)

Quantitative Statistical

Absorption [a.u.]

Wavelength [nm]

— DARPin

⋯ DARPin-FITC

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Fluorescence and imaging of proteins in cells (selected slides)

2.12 Genetically encoded photosensitizers

Erik Sedlák

Abstract: Flavin mononucleotide (FMN), as a very efficient photosensitizer producing singlet oxygen, $^1\text{O}_2$, is an indispensable part of the flavin-based genetically-encoded photosensitizers (GEPSs). However, an encapsulation of the isoalloxazine ring of FMN into the protein matrix significantly decreases its $^1\text{O}_2$ production efficiency. Although protein engineering aiming to decrease interactions of the isoalloxazine ring with surrounding amino acids led to an increase in $^1\text{O}_2$ production efficiency, it may lead to an undesirable weakening of the FMN-protein interaction in the native state. Here, we present an alternative approach how to address the issue of low $^1\text{O}_2$ production efficiency by GEPS. In our design, the interaction isoalloxazine ring-protein in the native state is affected only upon the protein irradiation and leads to FMN dissociation. This is achieved by placing cysteine, the $^1\text{O}_2$ oxidation-prone amino acid, in a proper position in the isoalloxazine ring binding site, which due to irradiation-induced sulfur oxidation of its residue increases volume and triggers FMN release. This concept has been successfully demonstrated in this work on three mutants of the LOV2 domain from *Avena sativa* (AsLOV2): V416C, T418C, and V416C/T418C. The $^1\text{O}_2$ production efficiency of the AsLOV2 strongly correlates with the efficiency of the irradiation-induced FMN dissociation from the variants in the order: wt<V416C<T418C<V416C/T418C.

Genetically encoded photosensitizers (selected slides)

Genetically-encoded photosensitizers

Light-induced ROS Generation and ROS-mediated Cell Destructions

Liao et al. (2014) Biomaterials 35, 500-508.

Genetically encoded HER2/neu-targeted photosensitizers. (A) Schematic presentation of selective cell ablation using 4D5scFv-miniSOG in HER2/neu-positive SKBR-3 cells and the absence of the effect in HER2/neu-negative CHO cells. (B) 4D5scFv-KillerRed dimeric immunophotosensitizer (4D5scFv PDB entry 1FCV, KillerRed PDB entry 3G83). (C) 4D5scFv-miniSOG immunophotosensitizer (miniSOG structure based on the closely related protein iLOV, PDB entry 4EET). Cofactor FMN is shown in red in the miniSOG chromophore pocket. (D) DARPin-miniSOG immunophotosensitizer based on DARPin_9-29 (PDB entry 4HRJ).

Schematic overview of CAI using miniSOG. MiniSOG and a target protein are expressed within a cell as a fusion protein. CAI is used for the spatio-temporal light-induced ROS generation by miniSOG, more likely inactivating a target protein in the close vicinity.

Souslova et al. (2017) J. Biophotonics 10, 338-352.

Genetically encoded photosensitizers (selected slides)

Genetically encoded photosensitizers (selected slides)

